

INFINITE LIFE OF CFRP EVALUATED NONDESTRUCTIVELY WITH X-RAY-REFRACTION TOPOGRAPHY

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1 Introduction

CFRP are more and more used in modern civil aircrafts hence the whole fuselage is made of this material (B787; A350). Due to strict certification standards finally the normal in-service loading gives a low stress level compared to the static and even the fatigue strength of the material. Hence CFRP are assumed to have an infinite life. To evaluate this assumption, fatigue tests on CFRP-specimens were performed up to 10^8 load cycles. The first inter-fiber failure was evaluated non-destructively by the fatigue tests accompanying X-ray-refraction topography [1, 2, 3, 4] alternately and in-situ mechanical loading. The basic idea of the investigation is represented in fig. 1. At low load levels it could not be assumed the total failure of the samples. Hence accompanying non-destructive testing (NDT) is mandatory to get information about the damage state of the material.

2 Materials and test specimen

The CFRP were made from a 200g/m² non-crimp fabric and 400g/m² twill style textile each made with Tenax-E HTA40 E1, 6K yarn. The matrix system was Huntsman Araldite® LY 556 / Aradur® 917 / Accelerator DY 070. Flat specimens with a length of 150mm, a width of 15mm (0°/90°-laminate) and 20mm (+/-45°-laminate) with a thickness of 1 and 2mm and tab reinforcement for clamping were used. 0°/90°- and +/-45°-laminates of each textile reinforcement were investigated. This paper focuses on the results made from the woven textiles. In general

the results from the non-crimp fabrics are quite similar however the comprehension of the experiments is not so complete. Hence only the measurements on the twill fabric are shown and discussed to enable a brief presentation.

3 Experimental

3.1 X-ray-refraction technique

X-ray refraction [2] is caused by the effect of refraction at the interface of materials of different refractive index as well known from visible light passing glass lenses. In the case of X-rays the refraction angle is below half a degree and in opposite direction due to the dispersion function of isolators. Hence Small Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS) technique is used. In the experimental set-up (s. fig. 2) a collimated X-ray beam passes the sample. At a fixed angle the refracted signal is measured and additionally a signal proportional to the absorption. A characteristic refraction value C is determined, which is proportional to the surface per unit volume. It can be calculated from the scattering I_R and transmitted intensities I_A and the thickness d of the sample in relation to the zero values (without sample):

$$C = \left[\frac{I_R/I_{R0}}{I_A/I_{A0}} - 1 \right] \cdot \frac{1}{d} \quad (1)$$

The intensity of the refracted beam will increase if a difference of the refractive index occurs at the observed interfaces. Hence, the intensity will be higher for materials with de-bonded fibers or pores than without (s. fig. 3). By calibration the absolute as

well as the relative inner surfaces C are measured. In most cases the relative increase is sufficient and used in the further investigations. Scanning the whole area of the sample gives a topographic map of inner surfaces (s. fig. 3 and 5). According to Lambert-Beer's law the absorption is a function of the density-proportional linear absorption coefficient μ and the thickness d of the sample:

$$I_A = I_{A0} \cdot e^{-\mu \cdot d} \quad (2)$$

For several applications it is practical to normalize equation 1 to $\ln(I_A/I_{A0})$ resulting in the relative specific surface C_m/μ , independent from variation of the number of fiber filaments due to non-perfect production of the fabrics.

The density itself contains no information about inner surfaces. In the experimental setup of the refraction technique the absorption and the refraction signals are measured in one shot. Hence, both can be mapped independently. In fig. 3 the absorption and refraction mapping of a Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) made of a twill fabric are compared. The absorption (s. fig. 3, left) maps only slight differences of the density. However, the refraction-signal (s. fig. 3, right) maps the micro cracks due to cyclic fatigue loading, which causes the refraction effect at the fiber matrix de-bonding due to inter-fiber failure. Thus, if there is no significant change of the density, it is impossible to detect any fiber matrix de-bonding with the classical X-ray-radiography which only uses the absorption proportional to mass.

3.2 Damage evaluation in-situ loading

A tensile testing machine was integrated in a small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) setup (s. fig. 4). X-ray refraction topography [1, 2, 3, 4] was performed while the CFRP-samples were tensile loaded. This non-destructive technique enables the detection of micro-cracking and inter-fiber failure especially for CFRP. For GFRP X-ray-refraction and in-situ loading has already been successfully used [2, 4]. Hence the increase of inner surfaces due to inter-fiber failure was measured and given as a function of the stress state. For $0^\circ/90^\circ$ -laminate the first inter-fiber failure occur at a stress level of approximately 300MPa. In steps of about 1kN the load was increased till the total failure. The tests were backed

by in-situ acoustic emission (AE) recording using a Physical Acoustics system with PICO-sensors (peak frequency 500kHz). The measurements (cumulative signal-energy shown in fig. 6) confirm the result by detecting a first distinct increase of AE with the first crack detected by X-ray-refraction. Hence the first inter-fiber failure was visualized at 300MPa it is assumed to reach the very high cycle (VHCF) range (s. fig. 1) for the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ -laminate at and below this value.

3.3 Fatigue tests and damage evaluation

Fatigue test were done in a servo-hydraulic 10kN tensile testing machine at 5 up to 100Hz ($0^\circ/90^\circ$ -laminate). The intrinsic heating at low load levels is insignificant and hence the recorded surface temperature rise is moderate until shortly before failure. Even for $\pm 45^\circ$ -laminate the increase of the surface temperature is only 7K at the lowest load-level of 50MPa and a test frequency of 50Hz. During all fatigue tests the surface temperature was recorded with an infrared sensor. A maximum temperature rise of 10K was accepted hence the maximum temperature inside the specimen could be assumed below 20K. That is far away from the glass transition temperature of about 120°C of this EP-matrix system. All tests were done air conditioned at 23°C and 50% humidity.

The fatigue tests were performed up to 10^8 load cycles. Accompanying X-ray refraction measurements of the samples were done to characterize the damage state and its evolution (s. fig. 2, 7, 9, 10).

In $0^\circ/90^\circ$ -laminates a high inter-fiber transverse loading occurs. In $\pm 45^\circ$ -laminates a high inter-fiber shear loading emerges. As the ambition of the project is to find the stress level of infinite life, inter-fiber failure has to be investigated.

$0^\circ/90^\circ$ -laminate

An overview of the fatigue tests on $0^\circ/90^\circ$ -specimen is summarized in fig. 7. The total failure of the samples emerged in the fatigue tests at and above 500MPa upper limit, load ratio $R=0,1$. At 300MPa inter-fiber failure occurs at the first load cycles however the specimens do not fail up to 10^7 and hence reach the VHCF region.

Below a stress level of 150MPa no increase of micro cracking could be observed up to 10^8 load cycles for

a $0^\circ/90^\circ$ - twill style fabric laminate at a load ratio of $R=0.1$ (s. fig. 7). This is approximately 50% of the inter-fiber failure stress in static loading (s. fig. 6). Thus technically infinite life could be assumed at this load level in respect to the laminate, the load ratio and the taken material concerning fiber, fabric and matrix.

In between 150 and 300 MPa upper limit stress there is a transition region from undamaged to damaged state evaluated with X-ray refraction and surface cracks by eye inspection. To find the boundary experiments at one stress level and in-situ NDT while fatigue loading should be done. However this technique was not available at this state of the project. Hence fatigue tests up to a certain number load cycles at different stress levels were performed and subsequent X-ray refraction scans were done. For 10^6 load cycles this is presented in fig. 7. At a stress of 200MPa and 10^6 load cycles the first micro-cracks / inter-fiber failure were found. Due to the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ -fiber orientation only X-ray-scans have to be done where the plane of collimation is perpendicular ($\omega=0^\circ$ in fig. 2) to the specimens length direction. Only the inter-fiber failure of the 90° -layer have to be investigated.

+/-45°-laminate

The overview of the fatigue tests on +/-45°-laminate is summarized in fig. 8. The failure in fatigue loading is found at and above a maximum stress of 70MPa up to 10^6 load cycles. The region of no damage is below 50MPa. That's also approximately 50% of inter-fiber shear strength. The VHCF region could be reached at an upper limit of stress of 60MPa.

Fortunately the scatter of number of load cycles to failure of the S-N-curve is much lower compared to the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ -laminate. Hence it seems to be possible to investigate the boundary from undamaged to damaged state by fatigue tests on a constant stress level of 75 and 60MPa. At pre-defined numbers of load-cycles the fatigue tests were stopped and X-ray-refraction mapping of inner surface / cracks were performed (see fig. 8 dotted line and fig. 9 and 10).

Due to the +/-45°-fiber orientation two perpendicular oriented X-ray refraction measurements have to be done [2, 3]. Two different failure mechanism occur. First perpendicular to the fiber length direction matrix cracks appear in the crossings of the fiber bundles and subsequent intralaminar fiber ma-

trix debonding occur due to the inter-fiber shear loading. Both effects can be distinguished by the perpendicular measurements. In parallel configuration (see fig. 9 und 10) only the fiber matrix debonding is visualized. In perpendicular configuration both – the fiber matrix debonding and the matrix cracks become visible. The scattering orientation function is proportional to $\cos^2\omega$ [2, 3]. Hence the +/-45°-fiber orientation and fiber-matrix de-bonding contribute each 50% of the signal of the measurements in parallel and perpendicular and consequently the matrix cracks contribute 100% to the perpendicular and 0% to the parallel-scanning configuration.

4. Discussion

It is well known [5] to visualize inter-fiber failure with the classical radiography at low X-ray energies, however contrast agent have to be used to mark them and only cracks connected to the sample surface will be detectable. With the X-ray refraction technique thin micro cracks and inter-fiber failure could be visualized without contrast agent averaged over the volume [1] and hence an in-situ investigation of increasing micro damages in parallel to mechanical static [2, 3] and fatigue loading is possible. Acoustic emission is a powerful tool to detect non-destructively inter-fiber failure and fiber failure in-situ mechanical loading. However due to the noise of the mechanical testing machines it is difficult to separate the right signal. Additionally acoustic emission could only measure the inter-fiber failure just in-situ in the moment it happens. Consequently a subsequent analysis offline is impossible. Finally a coupling of mechanical testing and X-ray-refraction was favored.

A stress level of 50% of static inter-fiber failure seems to be the limit to the infinite life of CFRP either for intralaminar transverse and shear loading. This is in the region where the airliners and wind-turbine blades are designed due to certification standards. Hence the fatigue of the composite materials play a secondary role regarding the fatigue life of such applications. Finally it has to be stated, that this results are only valid for the investigated materials. It has to be investigated the influence of the sizing of the fibers and the matrix to improve the limit of infinite life, regarding inter-fiber failure.

5. Conclusions

An infinite life was found for cyclic fatigue loaded CFRP-samples under high inter-fiber transverse ($0^\circ/90^\circ$ laminate) and shear ($\pm 45^\circ$ laminate) loading investigated up to 10^8 load cycles. Meanwhile state of the art is to take failure of the samples as the fatigue life. Accompanying non-destructive X-ray-refraction measurements reflects a level of damage even if samples failure never occurs. This results and investigation technique is of high interest to give the engineer a design value of infinite life which is practically often reached due to knock down factors of certification standards. Further investigations at different load ratios (especially $R=-1$) are running. A high influence of the load ratio on the stress level of infinite life is assumed and well known for the fatigue life of FRPs.

6. Acknowledgement

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Fig. 1: Basic idea of investigation

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Fig. 2: Experimental setup of the X-ray-refraction technique

Fig. 3: The absorption and refraction signal are measured at the same position on the sample. Only with respect to the refraction signal the cracks could be visualized.

Fig. 4: 15kN-elektromechanical tensile testing machine integrated in the X-ray scanner.

Fig. 5: X-ray-refraction scans of samples at different load levels and 1 million load-cycles.

Fig. 6: 0°/90°-CFRP-sample tensile loaded and in-situ accompanying X-ray-refraction and acoustic emission testing.

Fig. 7: S-N-curve of 0°/90°-CFRP specimens – failed, damaged and no detectable damage. Load ratio R=0,1

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Fig. 8: S-N-curve of +/-45°-CFRP specimens – failed, damaged and no detectable damage. Load ratio R=0,1

Fig. 9: Increase of micro-cracking in a +/-45°-CFRP specimen due to cyclic loading and analyzed with X-ray refraction parallel and perpendicular to the samples length direction. Maximum stress 75MPa and load ratio R=0,1

Fig. 10: Increase of micro-cracking in a +/-45°-CFRP specimen due to cyclic loading and analyzed with X-ray refraction parallel and perpendicular to the samples length direction. Maximum stress 60MPa and load ratio R=0,1